

Local Government in Poland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.2. The Provision of Local Public Transport

Andżelika Mirska, *University of Warsaw*

Relevance of the Practice

The task related to the provision of local public transport is a particularly important, highly debated issue in Poland. The main responsibility in this respect lies with the *gmina*, but also with the *powiat* and the voivodeship (in the scope of supracommunal connections). Before 1989, a state-owned enterprise PKS (Motor Transport Company) conducted business in Poland. It was a monopolist on the market but maintained a very dense network of local connections of high frequency. Residents were used to the availability of public transport (aside from its quality). Due to the political transformation, PKS lost its monopoly and the responsibility for transport in Poland was fragmented. Different self-governments deal with this task with varying degrees of success. It should be borne in mind that efficient public transport ensures access to other public services (access to education, health care, culture), especially for children and the elderly. It also has an impact on the quality of the environment (pollution, traffic jams in cities).

Description of the Practice

Urban and rural *gminas* face other problems and challenges regarding the provision of local and regional transport.

Rural *gminas* are confronted with the problem of insufficient transport connections. The drastic reduction in public transport led to the implementation of management according to the NPM (New Public Management) model, i.e. privatization of public transport enterprises. Private entrepreneurs were eliminating unprofitable connections in rural areas. As a result, a phenomenon of transport exclusion of residents has occurred (and thus limited access to work, education, health care, culture, etc.). Residents of rural areas try to cope with this situation by purchasing cars (import of used, cheap cars). In some *gminas* there are more than 3,000 cars per 3,500 residents. This in turn poses the problem of air pollution and the utilization of old cars.

The NIK (Supreme Audit Office) report of 18 April 2016 shows that self-governments are not able to handle the statutory task of ensuring public transport.²⁰

²⁰ Department of Infrastructure, 'Funkcjonowanie regionalnego pasażerskiego transportu drogowego' (*Najwyższa Izba Kontroli*, 25 May 2016) <<https://www.nik.gov.pl/plik/id,10841,vp,13179.pdf>> accessed 10 July 2019.

The scale of the problem with local transport is different in urban areas, agglomerations and metropolitan areas. The problem here is how to organize a common transport network across administrative boundaries.

Assessment of the Practice

The scale of the problem with local transport is different in urban areas, agglomerations and metropolitan areas. The problem here is how to organize a common transport network across administrative boundaries.

This problem can be solved by the cooperation of self-governments. Since 2016, the unions of *gmina-powiat* may be established. Eight such unions have been formed, seven of which concern the common organization of public transport.

However, only 18 inter-communal unions out of 313 have public transport within the scope of their activity, of which 8 unions were established for one purpose only, i.e. public transport (the others are multi-purpose, e.g. environmental protection, sewerage, tourism, etc.)²¹.

Therefore, the task of *gmina* self-government, which is to provide public transport, has various effects in the course of the operation of urban and rural self-governments. Rural self-governments encounter the problem of transport exclusion of residents (elimination of connections, lack of transport in general – lack of financial resources). Urban self-governments face the challenge of agglomeration and metropolitanization processes – the expectations of residents regarding common transport and fares valid beyond the administrative boundaries of *gminas* and *powiats*. When considering this task from a broader perspective, it may be treated as an activity intended to improve the mobility of residents. The domain of urban self-governments is innovative activities, such as the city bicycle system or the rental of city electric cars.

Performing this task affects the financial situation of self-governments (report section 3), may lead to structural changes through the formation of unions of self-governments to provide common transport services or to the cooperation with private entities under PPPs (report section 4). In view of the crisis in that area, the Polish Central Government has recently been very active and announced a program of financial support for self-governments. To the disappointment of the *gminas*, the voivodeship self-government (report section 5) will be the administrator of the funds. In this respect, the self-government may appeal directly to the

²¹ 'Zarejestruj, zmień statut lub wyrejestruj związek międzygminny, związek powiatów, związek powiatowo-gminny' (Ministry of the Interior and Administration, 2 July 2019) <<https://www.gov.pl/web/mswia/zarejestruj-zmien-statut-lub-wyrejestruj-zwiazek-miedzygminny-zwiazek-powiatow-zwiazek-powiatowo-gminny>> accessed 10 July 2019.

residents, e.g. local referendums in Kraków and Wrocław on the construction of the underground railway (report section 6).

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